
Self-Affirmative Discourse on the Use of Digital Platforms for Mental Health Advocacy

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Abstract

This paper is a self-affirmative on the use of digital platforms for mental health advocacy and education. The researchers adopted library research method. No form of empirical research was conducted as the researchers mainly relied secondary sources like textbooks, journals, newspapers, online materials and other secondary sources. The discourse showed that success of digital-driven mental health advocacy and education hinges on user engagement and experience. The discourse further showed designing user-friendly interfaces, interactive features and personalised content contributes to sustained engagement. It encourages applications and platforms prioritising user experience as it foster increased participation, information retention and ongoing involvement in mental health conversations. It was concluded that the effectiveness of digital platforms in mental health advocacy and education is contingent upon navigating various factors, including accessibility, user engagement, privacy, cultural sensitivity and collaborative partnerships. Addressing these factors ensures a more comprehensive, inclusive and impactful utilisation of technology to advance mental health advocacy efforts, ultimately contributing to a more informed, connected and supportive society. Thus, mental health advocacy efforts should prioritise widely used platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp and youtube, which are popular in many parts of Nigeria.

Keywords: Digital Media, Mental Health, Advocacy, Education